

Study of hydrogen bonding interactions of methaqualone with alcohols, naphthols (α and β) and nitrophenols

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Abstract : Methaqualone is a non-addictive drug widely abused by the miscreants. However, the principle of drug action is not known with certainty. H-bonding appears to be an important property for drug action. Methaqualone is found to form H-bonds with alcohols, naphthols, nitrophenol as apparent from the determination of the association constants of methaqualone with the ligands. Attempt has been made to suggest a probable mechanism of drug action based on water structure, H-bonding and hydrophobic interactions.

Keywords : Methaqualone, hydrogen bonding, naphthols, alcohols, drug mechanism.

Introduction

Methaqualone was introduced as 'non-addictive' sleeping pills or sedative hypnotic drug with pharmacological effects similar to those of barbiturates such as Phenobarbital, a CNS depressant^{1,2}. The effects include a reduction of mental activity, cardiac and respiratory depression. However, prolonged use causes psychological and physical dependence of the drug i.e. methaqualone causes addiction and the severities of withdrawal symptoms were similar to those of barbiturates and it is now an illicit drug³.

Methaqualone has been found to be abused by miscreants who rob the passengers of their belongings by inducing sleep by offering them toffees, tea, coffee (or alcohols) mixed with methaqualone⁴.

The physico-chemical principle of drug action of methaqualone is not known with certainty. Drug action is known to be due to physico-chemical interactions of drugs with the receptor molecules triggering biological action. The reactions, usually reversible weak interactions like charge transfer, H-bonding, hydrophobic or Van der Waals interactions play dominant role.

The interactions are weak but multiplicity of interactions cause stabilization of the 'drug receptor complex'. However, a particular interaction or bond formation usually has a decisive influence though it is not possible to ascertain the actual forces involved³. H-bonding interactions and hydrophobic interactions are two important forces and their study is worth pursuing.

These considerations led us to study the hydrogen bonding interactions of methaqualone with alcohols, *p*-nitrophenol, α - and β -naphthols.

The results are reported in this paper.

Experimental

Purification of drug : Methaqualone (from Sigma, Central Drug House, Kolkata, India having purity >99%) was dissolved in methanol and crystallized twice. *p*-Nitrophenol (G.R., E. Merck) was purified by sublimation. α - and β -naphthols (G.R., E. Merck) were purified by recrystallization from dry ether. Ethanol (Absolute G.R., E. Merck, Germany) was taken as such. Methanol and carbon tetrachloride (Spectroscopic Grade, Spectrochem) were used as such.

Purity of the samples was checked by melting point determination.

Methaqualone, naphthols, nitrophenol absorb strongly in the UV region. The spectra of the acceptors, drugs and mixtures of acceptors and drug, spectra of drug with alcohols were taken in CCl_4 .

The solvent shifts of methaqualone were examined in water, methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, hexane and benzene (Table 1).

Some typical absorption curves are presented in Figs. 1-6. The absorption characteristics are given in Tables 2a and 2b.

The spectra indicate shift and changes in the optical

Table 1. Solvent shift effect of methaqualone in different solvent

Solvent taken	λ_{\max} (nm) for $1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$ methaqualone
Water	265
Methanol	275
Ethanol	277
Isopropanol	266
Chloroform	268, 240, 235
Carbontetrachloride	319, 307, 270
Hexane	268, 262, 256, 250
Benzene	279, 272, 269, 256

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of (a) methaqualone, (b) nitrophenol and (c) complex of methaqualone + nitrophenol.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of (a) methaqualone, (b) α -naphthol and (c) complex of methaqualone + α -naphthol.

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of (a) methaqualone, (b) β -naphthol and (c) complex of methaqualone + β -naphthol.

Fig. 4. Absorption spectra of methaqualone at different concentrations ranges from $1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ in CCl_4 .

densities. For hydrogen bonding with alcohols, different amounts of methaqualone ($1 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $4 \times 10^{-5} M$) in carbon tetrachloride were mixed with excess of methanol and ethanol but at different concentrations. For studying hydrogen bonding and weak interactions of naphthols, nitrophenol complexes with methaqualone, equal concentrations ($1 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $4 \times 10^{-5} M$) of the components were mixed in stoichiometric ratios.

The optical densities of the complexes and the components were measured at the desired wavelengths to calculate K_{DA} . The values are given in Tables 2a and 2b.

Measurements were taken at 298 K with a Shimadzu Double Beam UV-Visible Spectrophotometer (Model UV

Fig. 5. Absorption spectra of methaqualone + methanol at different concentrations in CCl_4 .

Fig. 6. Absorption spectra of methaqualone + ethanol at different concentrations in CCl_4 .

2550) with thermoelectrically temperature controlled cell compartment.

Results

Assuming 1 : 1 complex formation between the drugs (D) (donors) and the ligands (A) (acceptors), the association constant for the reaction,

can be written as

$$K_{DA} = \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} \cdot \frac{\gamma_{DA}}{\gamma_D \cdot \gamma_A} \approx \frac{x}{(C_1 - x)(C_2 - x)} \quad (2)$$

In view of non-electrolytic nature of the reactants and complexes and at low concentrations $\gamma_{DA}/\gamma_D \cdot \gamma_A$ (γ represents activity coefficients of the respective species) can be regarded to be unity. C_1 and C_2 represent the initial concentrations of D and A respectively, x represent the equilibrium concentration of the complex DA .

The usual procedure of determining K_{DA} using Benesi-Hildebrand⁵ or Scott⁶ equation have been avoided and an iterative procedure⁷⁻¹² using the equation,

$$\frac{C_1}{(d - d_1 - d_2)} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)l} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)(C_2 - x)l} \cdot \frac{1}{K_{DA}} \quad (3)$$

(where $l = 1 \text{ cm}$)

was used for the determination of association constants between methaqualone and naphthols.

Table 2a. λ_{max} , equilibrium constant (K), extinction coefficient (ϵ) and free energy (ΔG^0), values for complexes between methaqualone and different acceptors at 298 K in carbontetrachloride

Name of drug	λ_{max} of drug (nm)	Acceptors	λ_{max} of acceptors (nm)	λ_{max} of complexes (nm)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-4}$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) at 25 °C	ϵ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	$\log K_{DA}$	$-\Delta G^0$ (kJ mol^{-1})
Methaqualone	319	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	250, 307	281	171.6	26624	6.234	35.57
	307	α -Naphthol	256, 284, 324	306	7.55	10696	4.878	27.83
	270	β -Naphthol	287, 330	268	10.33	24470	5.014	28.60

Table 2b. λ_{max} , equilibrium constant (K) and free energy (ΔG^0) values for hydrogen bonded complexes between methaqualone and alcohols at 298 K in carbontetrachloride

Name of drug	λ_{max} of drug (nm)	Alcohols	λ_{max} of hydrogen bonded complexes (nm)	K_{DA} ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) at 25 °C	$\log K_{DA}$	$-\Delta G^0$ (kJ mol^{-1})
Methaqualone	319	MeOH	275	5.697	0.755	4.3
	307					
	270	EtOH	277	0.685	-0.164	-0.94

$$\text{Here, } d_1 = \varepsilon_1 C_1 l \quad (4)$$

$$d_2 = \varepsilon_2 C_2 l \quad (5)$$

$$d = \varepsilon x l + \varepsilon_1 (C_1 - x)l + \varepsilon_2 (C_2 - x)l \quad (6)$$

All the components and the complexes absorb strongly in the UV region.

Thus,

$$x = \frac{d - d_1 - d_2}{(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2)l} \quad (7)$$

when *A* is present in large excess (as in case of alcohol complexes) and does not absorb (i.e. $d_2 = 0$), the expression (3) reduces to

$$\frac{C_1}{(d - d_1)} = \frac{1}{(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_1)l} + \frac{1}{(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_1)(C_2)l} \cdot \frac{1}{K_{DA}} \quad (8)$$

An iterative method was adopted for the calculations of equilibrium constants K_{DA} at 298 K in the way given before. K_{DA} and related values are recorded in Tables 2a and 2b. ΔG° values were calculated from the relation,

$$\Delta G = -2.303RT \log K_{DA} \quad (9)$$

Discussion

Structure of methaqualone is depicted below :

Methaqualone can be regarded to be a π -electron donor as well as $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ donor. It has three absorption bands (except in alcohols), the band near 270 nm is due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition whereas the bands at 307 and 319 nm are due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions and it can act as proton acceptor.

The bands at 250 nm and 256 nm for *p*-nitrophenol and α naphthol are due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions where the bands near 307 nm (*p*-nitrophenol, 284 nm (324 nm) (α -naphthol) and 287 nm and 330 nm (β -naphthol) are due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. These compounds are well known for their H-bonding capabilities. Methaqualone when mixed with these compounds show slight or appreciable blue shift with marked changes in o.d. values with respect to methaqualone and other H-bonding compounds and alcohols.

Coggeshall and Long¹³, Nagakura and Baba¹⁴, Basu

and Bhowmik¹⁵⁻¹⁸ observed shifts of the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition for the bonds of phenols due to hydrogen bond formation. The correlation of the association constants of the drug complexes with the pK_a values of the ligands as done by Basu and co-workers¹⁵⁻¹⁸ were not attempted as pK_a values of ligands refer to the proton donating capability of phenols and naphthols in aqueous solution where ionization, solute-solvent interactions and hydrophobic interactions etc. are important. The pK_a values of the ligands in water have no relevance in CCl_4 where many of the interactions are absent or have no or different meaning. Proton donating capabilities also change in other solvents.

The association constants between methaqualone with *p*-nitrophenol and α and β naphthols are high and is in the order :

whereas in case of alcohols, the association constants are low and the values are in the order :

In the former case, concentrations of the compounds are in the stoichiometric ratios and the expression for the association constant is,

$$K_{DA} = \frac{x}{(C_1 - x)(C_2 - x)}$$

and the values are high. But in the latter case, the concentrations of the alcohols are high and in large excess and the expression for the association constant is,

$$K_{DA} = \frac{x}{(C_1 - x)C_2} \quad \text{where } C_2 \gg C_1 \text{ and } x$$

However, K values determined using $D \gg A$ are likely to be in error and the accurate values are obtainable using D and A in stoichiometric ratios. Foster¹⁹ also made similar observation.

The results suggest fairly strong hydrogen bond formation of methaqualone with H-bonding agents. It is known that chemical structure of the drugs, their physico-chemical and pharmacological properties are interrelated. Therefore, an attempt to explore the mechanism of drug action has been made.

The physiological and chemical explanation for the sedative - hypnotic drug like methaqualone is not known with certainty. But the sedatives usually impede neurotransmission and take a much larger stimulus to evoke res-

ponse. Methaqualone consists of aromatic rings, two N-atoms, C=O groups and CH₃ groups. It is lipophilic in nature and capable of undergoing CT interactions, hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions with suitable donors or acceptors i.e the drug-receptor interaction is a definite possibility. In laboratory experiments with CCl₄ as solvent, hydrophobic interaction is absent but in biological systems where water is one of the principal components, hydrophobic interaction plays a dominant role.

Biointeractions are extremely complex. H-bonding is particularly important to control the activities of the biological world due to interplay of self associating and directional properties of water and hydrophobic properties of biomolecular macro molecules like proteins, nucleic acid etc. The unbalanced nature of water, its co-operativity, co-planarity and orientation dependent properties helps the biomolecules (like receptors) to fold, assume shapes and assemble and it is responsible for the self association or self assembly of biomolecules which give them extreme specificity and complexity for bioreactions²⁰. These properties are lost in organic solvents. Water also controls the hydration of ions and ion channels.

Thus, water through H-bonding and hydration of ions control the bioactivity of neurotransmitters forming a definite structural entity. H-bonds are relatively weak and are transient in nature persisting only for a few tens of picoseconds (10⁻¹² s)²¹ and there is continuous making or breaking of H-bonds. However, the structural arrangement of the neurotransmitters is likely to be disrupted with the introduction of methaqualone resulting in the reorientation and disruption of the water molecules due to the hydrogen bonding around the neurotransmitters and ion channels. Methaqualone (administered as hydrochlorides or as such) due to its lipophilic nature cross the water/lipid membrane or gastric mucosa by active partition technique.

It may undergo a number of biological transformation and a part will move with plasma proteins and cross the blood brain barrier and gain access to the CNS to cause pharmacological effect.

But the structural disruption and reordering of the solvent molecules across blood brain barrier by hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions by the lipophilic methaqualone appears to be the reason for impeding neu-

rotransmission causing sedative action. The results can be corroborated by comparing the importance of H-bonding in biological systems as given below³ :

(i) Stabilization of DNA molecule due to multiple hydrogen bonding between complimentary base pairs (A-T and G-C pairs) in the DNA helix.

(ii) Stabilization of the tertiary structures of proteins due to the formation of N-H---O bonds.

Rupture of the H-bonds by strong H-bonding agents will disrupt or destroy the DNA helix or tertiary structures of proteins. Due to transient existence of H-bonding, the drug is expected to be eliminated rapidly and drugs are more addictive, the faster they are cleared from the body²².

References

1. A. Martin, "Physical Pharmacy", International student ed., Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, Philadelphia, 4th ed., 2001 (reprint), pp. 265-267.
2. A. Albert, "Selective Toxicity", 6th ed., Chapman and Hall, London, pp. 516-518.
3. R. F. Doerge, "Wilson and Gisvold's Text Book of Organic Medicinal and Pharmaceutical Chemistry", 8th ed., Lippincott Company, Philadelphia, 1986.
4. (a) J. A. Seigel, P. J. Saukko and G. C. Knupfer in : "The Encyclopedia of Forensic Sciences", edited by Academic Press, New York, 2000; (b) D. K. Kuila, B. Mukhopadhyaya and S. C. Lahiri, *Forensic Sci. Communication*, 2006, 8, No.4 [http://www.fbi.gov/hq/lab/fsc/backissu/oct2006/research/2006_10_research02.htm].
5. H. A. Benesi and J. H. Hildebrand, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2703.
6. R. L. Scott, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas. Belg.*, 1956, 75, 787.
7. S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 715.
8. K. K. Majumder and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, 73, 163; 1997, 74, 378; 2000, 77, 447.
9. R. Mondal (Karan) and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1998, 205, 69.
10. R. Mondal (Karan) and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, 76, 347.
11. J. Gangopadhyay and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 2001, 215, 37, 837.
12. D. K. Kuila and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, 81, 928.
13. N. D. Coggeshall and G. M. Lang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3283.
14. S. Nagakura and H. Baba, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952,

- 74, 5693.
15. A. K. Chandra and S. Basu, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, **56**, 632.
 16. B. B. Bhowmik and S. Basu, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1962, **58**, 48.
 17. B. B. Bhowmik and S. Basu, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, **59**, 813.
 18. B. B. Bhowmik, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 4442.
 19. R. Foster, "Organic Charge-transfer Complexes", Academic Press, London and New York, 1969, Chap. 7.
 20. M. Morra, ed., *Water in Biomaterial Surface Science - Introduction*.
 21. E. A. Vogler, "Water in Biomaterial Surface Science", ed. M. Morra, Chap. 1.
 22. "The Biochemical Basis of Neuropharmacology" by Cooper, Bloom and Roth, The Eaton T. Fores Research Centre, 2002 [<http://www.etfrc.com/benzos.htm>].